

Deliverable 3.3. Predictive DL model capable of multi-mutation predictions of protein fitness

Protein engineering is a field dedicated to modifying proteins to improve their performance, whether for industrial, medical, or research purposes. One of the biggest challenges in this field is predicting how changes in a protein's sequence – known as mutations –, will affect its ability to function—this ability is often referred to as “protein fitness.” Deliverable D3.3 details how industrial partner Bio-Product has developed an advanced artificial intelligence (AI) system that predicts how proteins will behave when mutated, even when multiple mutations are involved. This system relies on a framework that uses deep learning (DL) and a special method such as multi-objective learning to handle various tasks simultaneously. We also incorporated cutting-edge insights from biological datasets, enabling the system to predict protein behavior better than existing methods.

- At the core of our platform is an AI system that can learn from vast amounts of protein data to predict how changes in their sequences will impact their fitness. By training the AI to differentiate between very similar protein sequences, even with subtle differences, we have made the predictions much more accurate. This is especially useful for understanding the combined effects of multiple mutations, where predicting fitness has historically been very difficult.
- The AI does not just predict single mutations; it can design new proteins by combining many mutations too. By understanding how sequences of amino acids (the building blocks of proteins) impact protein fitness, we can develop new protein variants that are better suited for various applications, such as enzymes for pharmaceutical companies. We have a number of real-world success stories where our designed proteins were significantly more effective than the ones developed by the competing and in-house methodologies.
- State-of-the-art performance: Our platform, enhanced by datasets like the Helix Pathogenicity scores, outperformed existing methods in predicting protein behavior. The combination of diverse training data and advanced AI modeling makes our system one of the most accurate available today.

We plan to integrate more experimental data, improving the accuracy of our models even further. By constantly refining our approach and incorporating new biological insights, we aim to revolutionize protein engineering and pave the way for more effective designs in fields ranging from pharmaceuticals to renewable energy.

In summary, by combining cutting-edge AI technology with deep biological insights, our platform is leading the way in predicting and designing proteins that can meet the complex demands of modern science and industry.